

1 **Optimising outbreak investigation, surveillance and discovery of**
2 **pathogens in aquaculture using unbiased metagenomics**

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17 **Abstract**

18 Emerging infectious diseases are a major threat to global aquaculture production and are
19 projected to increase in frequency due to anthropogenic stressors and climate change. Our
20 ability to screen the global aquatic “infectome” is dramatically improving through unbiased
21 metatranscriptomic (i.e. total RNA) sequencing. Despite recent advances in molecular
22 diagnostics and next-generation sequencing, outbreak investigation in aquaculture often
23 encounters limitations due to the targeted nature of conventional techniques, which may only
24 capture a small portion of the diverse array of disease-causing agents present in nature,
25 sometimes requiring years to resolve. Here, we propose that unbiased metatranscriptomic
26 sequencing serves as a cost-effective technique for rapidly characterising pathogens during
27 disease outbreaks and in surveillance programs. In doing so, we offer a systematic diagnostic
28 framework – with high analytical sensitivity and specificity – to mitigate infectious disease
29 threats to global aquaculture. We emphasize the importance of combining rapid
30 metatranscriptomics with traditional techniques for a holistic examination into the causes of
31 unknown aetiologies in aquatic animals, and how it can be used to examine host responses in
32 parallel with pathogen discovery. We suggest that the integration of metatranscriptomics into
33 aquaculture will require upskilling, proficiency testing, user-friendly bioinformatic tools, and
34 open data sharing. Furthermore, it is essential to establish a reporting framework – with
35 analytical guidelines – that ensures the protection of animal industries while safeguarding
36 trade interests.

37 **The emergence of infectious diseases in aquaculture**

38 Aquaculture is the most rapidly growing primary industry globally, valued at 312 billion US
39 dollars¹. Over the last 60 years, the average global consumption of seafood has more than
40 doubled and is expected to rise – the so called “blue revolution” is advancing at a remarkable
41 pace¹. Importantly, however, the rapid expansion of aquaculture coincides with the
42 emergence of notable infectious diseases in aquatic animals: the international trade introduces
43 pathogens to new geographic areas previously declared “disease-free” and exposes them to
44 densely populated animal monocultures that often experience high levels of stress and
45 immunosuppression². Furthermore, aquacultural systems facilitate a high degree of
46 connectivity at the domestic-wild interface through the utilisation of open net cages and
47 coastal ponds and in some industries wild sourced larvae, juveniles, and broodstock³⁻⁵. As
48 such, the rate of infectious disease emergence in aquatic animals is anticipated to increase in
49 frequency due to ongoing anthropogenic stressors and most notably, climate change⁶. Indeed,
50 epidemiological models have predicted that a simple 1°C increase in water temperature could
51 lead to a 6% increase in mortalities caused by finfish and crustacean viruses⁷.

52 The World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) currently lists 31 notifiable diseases of
53 aquatic animals of which 58% comprise infections caused by viruses, 32% eukaryotes, and
54 10% bacteria, respectively (Table 1)⁸. However, these known pathogens likely constitute only
55 a small portion of the broader spectrum of disease-causing agents present in the global
56 aquatic environment. A single indication is that a metatranscriptomic (i.e. total RNA
57 sequencing) analysis of finfish occupying a spatially restricted – 100 square metre –
58 community in the Great Barrier Reef, Australia, revealed a diverse array of 38 fish viruses
59 from 14 viral families, including the *Rhabdoviridae* and *Iridoviridae*⁹. Similarly,
60 environmental RNA (eRNA) from 50 ml of sediment material collected from a pond revealed
61 a remarkable 6.7 million viral RNA reads (i.e. transcripts), spanning 13 viral families
62 including the *Nodaviridae* and *Birnaviridae* that are common families of aquatic animal
63 pathogens (e.g. nervous necrosis virus and infectious pancreatic necrosis virus)¹⁰. It is also
64 notable that the aquatic environment is rich in opportunistic bacteria that similarly pose an
65 emerging threat, particularly in the context of climate change¹¹.

66 Although epidemiological models are designed to predict the dispersal and transmission of
67 aquatic pathogens, they are heavily biased towards a limited set of known viruses, bacteria
68 and parasites, particularly those listed as notifiable by the WOAH^{12,13}. Importantly, while our
69 understanding of microbial diversity – particularly viruses – is improving through

70 metatranscriptomic sequencing, the aquatic “infectome” is still vastly under characterised; it
 71 is unclear which pathogen will emerge at any given point. For example, the *Hantaviridae*, a
 72 family of negative-sense single-stranded RNA viruses, were traditionally thought to solely
 73 infect mammals, however, distant relatives were recently discovered in finfish (now known
 74 as “actinoviruses”)¹⁴. Shortly after these discoveries, an actinovirus was associated with gill
 75 disease, anorexia and skin ulcerations in farmed European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*)¹⁵. It is
 76 highly likely that infectious agents will emerge over time from the background pool of
 77 potential pathogens that exists in nature. As such, an unbiased framework is crucial for
 78 identifying emerging infectious diseases in aquaculture.

Table 1. Notifiable disease listed by the WOA⁸.

Disease	Host	Type
Infection with <i>Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis</i>	Amphibians	Eukaryote
Infection with <i>Batrachochytrium salamandrivorans</i>	Amphibians	Eukaryote
Infection with <i>Ranavirus</i> species	Amphibians	Virus
Infection with <i>Hepatobacter penaei</i> (necrotising hepatopancreatitis)	Crustaceans	Bacteria
Acute hepatopancreatic necrosis disease (<i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i>)	Crustaceans	Bacteria
Infection with <i>Aphanomyces astaci</i> (crayfish plague)	Crustaceans	Eukaryote
Infection with taura syndrome virus	Crustaceans	Virus
Infection with white spot syndrome virus	Crustaceans	Virus
Infection with yellow head virus (genotype 1)	Crustaceans	Virus
Infection with infectious hypodermal and haematopoietic necrosis virus	Crustaceans	Virus
Infection with <i>Macrobrachium rosenbergii</i> nodavirus (white tail disease)	Crustaceans	Virus
Infection with infectious myonecrosis virus	Crustaceans	Virus
Infection with decapod iridescent virus 1	Crustaceans	Virus
Infection with <i>Aphanomyces invadans</i> (epizootic ulcerative syndrome)	Fish	Eukaryote

Infection with <i>Gyrodactylus salaris</i>	Fish	Eukaryote
Infection with epizootic haematopoietic necrosis virus	Fish	Virus
Infection with infectious haematopoietic necrosis virus	Fish	Virus
Infection with spring viraemia of carp virus	Fish	Virus
Infection with viral haemorrhagic septicaemia virus	Fish	Virus
Infection with infectious salmon anaemia virus	Fish	Virus
Infection with red sea bream iridovirus	Fish	Virus
Infection with koi herpesvirus	Fish	Virus
Infection with salmonid alphavirus	Fish	Virus
Infection with tilapia lake virus	Fish	Virus
Infection with <i>Xenohaliotis californiensis</i>	Molluscs	Bacteria
Infection with <i>Bonamia ostreae</i>	Molluscs	Eukaryote
Infection with <i>Bonamia exitiosa</i>	Molluscs	Eukaryote
Infection with <i>Marteilia refringens</i>	Molluscs	Eukaryote
Infection with <i>Perkinsus marinus</i>	Molluscs	Eukaryote
Infection with <i>Perkinsus olseni</i>	Molluscs	Eukaryote
Infection with abalone herpesvirus	Molluscs	Virus

79 **The impact of biased screening and limitations of current approaches**

80 Critically, responses to disease outbreaks are often limited to pathogens listed by the WOA
81 and are screened using a variety of visual and molecular techniques including histopathology,
82 microscopy, cell culture, serology, and most notably PCR^{8,16}. Although PCR is a sensitive
83 approach, it requires the known sequence of a pathogen for the synthesis of primers and will
84 obviously fail to identify novel pathogens, particularly viruses. Similarly, while cell culture is
85 an effective method, as it allows for the detection of cytopathic effects *in vitro*, not all viruses

86 can be cultured, and despite the increasing availability of cell lines, they are insufficient to
87 characterise the large diversity of viruses that exist in nature^{2,9,14}. Such limitations are
88 reflected in the emergence of notable pathogens in fish that were discovered several years
89 after they emerged. Indeed, there remains a variety of unresolved diseases in aquatic
90 animals¹⁷.

91 A case in point is the emergence of heart and skeletal muscle inflammation (HSMI), that was
92 first recorded in 1999 in Norway^{18,19}. Diagnostic tests such as cell culture, histopathology,
93 electron microscopy, and PCR screening for a variety of suspected pathogens (e.g. infectious
94 salmon anaemia virus), yielded evidently negative results²⁰. Over a decade after the initial
95 outbreak, a novel reovirus – now known as piscine orthoreovirus – was identified through
96 next-generation sequencing and established as the causative agent of HSMI²¹. In a similar
97 manner, tilapia lake virus (TiLV) was responsible for severe disease outbreaks in 2009, but
98 wasn't discovered until 2014 following unsuccessful screening for known pathogens²². By
99 the time TiLV was characterised, it had already spread to South America and by 2020 it had
100 spread to 16 countries spanning four continents²³. In Egypt alone, TiLV was responsible for
101 production losses of 98,000 tonnes, valued at 100 million US dollars in 2015²⁴.

102 Other scenarios have unfolded in aquaculture industries when an easily detectable pathogen
103 was incorrectly identified as the causative agent. This led to ineffective antibiotic use and
104 allowed the actual virus to spread to new regions. For example, scale drop syndrome in Asian
105 sea bass (*Lates calcarifer*), first reported in 1992 by Malaysian farmers, was initially
106 attributed to *Tenacibaculum maritimum*, despite ineffective antibiotic treatments^{25,26}. In 2015,
107 the true cause, a new *Megalocytivirus* named scale drop disease virus (SDDV, now known as
108 *Megalocytivirus lates I*), was identified by using an unbiased virus discovery amplification
109 method and next-generation sequencing²⁶. During the 23 years from first farmer reports to
110 discovering the virus, SDDV spread to new regions (e.g. Indonesia, Singapore, Thailand, and
111 China) and hosts (yellowfin sea bream, *Acanthopagrus latus*)^{25,27,28} and today is considered a
112 significant disease threat in Asian aquaculture.

113 **Application of metatranscriptomics within a framework of outbreak** 114 **investigation**

115 The advent of metagenomic and in particular metatranscriptomic (i.e. total RNA) next-
116 generation sequencing has revolutionised our ability to screen the global aquatic
117 infectome^{14,29}. Metatranscriptomics provides a rapid, unbiased taxonomic view of RNA

118 viruses – which are often the source of emerging diseases – as well as DNA viruses, bacteria
 119 and parasites, in turn providing extraordinary amounts of microbial data that cannot be
 120 achieved by DNA sequencing alone (Figure 1)³⁰. Metatranscriptomics offers several key
 121 advantages: (i) it is cost effective as it can reveal the genomes of several novel or existing
 122 pathogens in a single test; (ii) it doesn't require the known sequence of a pathogen; (iii) it can
 123 detect pathogens at the variant level; and (iv) it can identify pathogens in parallel with the
 124 expression of host genes allowing for the detection of sub-clinical or pre-clinical infections
 125 based on signature host responses to disease agents and other stressors (Figure 1).

126 **Figure 1. Application of metagenomics/metatranscriptomics in the context of outbreak**
 127 **investigation in aquatic animal health.** Following case definition and the exclusion of
 128 environmental causes (e.g. water quality, pollution, algal blooms) (stage I), samples are collected in
 129 accordance with epidemiological investigation protocols and examined using traditional diagnostic
 130 procedures (stage II). If an aetiological agent is not fully determined during stage II, samples are then
 131 analysed using metatranscriptomics: total RNA is extracted, and following library preparation, next-
 132 generation sequencing is performed. Raw sequence reads are assembled into contigs and a similarity
 133 search (i.e. BLAST) against a database (e.g. NCBI nt/nr) is performed to identify a putative pathogen.
 134 The resultant contigs are mapped to the raw sequence reads and transcript abundance (e.g. reads per
 135 million) and coverage are calculated. Sequences with strong matches (e.g. e-value, bitscore,

136 percentage identity) to suspected pathogens are validated using phylogenetic methods. Following
137 sequence validation, *in vitro* or *in vivo* studies are performed to support the data generated from stages
138 II (e.g. histological lesions) and III and demonstrate causation. These additional procedures confirm
139 infection and inform the application of rationale control measures.

140 Metagenomics is immediately applicable in cases where routine diagnostic approaches fail to
141 identify the causative agent of an infectious disease or where diagnostic laboratories,
142 particularly in developing economies, lack the necessary expertise and technical capacity. It
143 may be the first case report of a newly emerged infectious disease or a complex disease
144 investigation where multiple and/or persistent pathogens are identified without pinpointing
145 the primary cause of the disease. For example, in Indonesia, farmers reported a ‘new’ disease
146 syndrome affecting grouper, marked by greenish discoloration to the head and body and high
147 mortality (e.g. 80-90%) within one month after transfer to sea cages³¹. A high prevalence of
148 ectoparasites and persistent viral infections made it challenging to identify a primary cause of
149 the mortality. Using a similar framework to Figure 1 – combining traditional and emerging
150 diagnostic approaches – the primary cause of the mortality was attributed to *Infectious spleen*
151 *and kidney necrosis virus* (ISKNV; now known as *Megalocytivirus pagrus 1*)³¹.

152 Rational use of metagenomics requires that an outbreak investigation has already been
153 conducted to confirm a likely infectious cause, and that appropriate investigations have ruled
154 out obvious or common aetiologies. Outbreak investigation commences with recognition that
155 there is a problem (i.e. verifying that an outbreak is in fact occurring). First reported in 1995
156 in the USA³², *Santee-Cooper ranavirus* (SCRV; now known as *Ranavirus micropterus 1*)
157 emerged in China in 2006, with identification of the virus as the cause of an ulcerative
158 syndrome³³. The diagnosis was delayed for several years despite the availability of molecular
159 diagnostic tests presumably as it was not known to occur in this region. The detection of
160 known pathogens in new areas could be accelerated with the use of metatranscriptomics,
161 improving fish welfare and saving costs. In large commercial enterprises this may be when
162 production data fail to meet benchmarks (e.g., weight gain per week or reduced feed
163 conversion efficiencies) or background mortalities exceed a certain accepted threshold.
164 However, since small-scale enterprises constitute ~80% of Asia's aquaculture volume¹ initial
165 reports often come from farmers experiencing high mortality, as seen with SDDV in
166 Malaysia²⁶, SCRV in China³³ and ISKNV in Indonesia³¹. In wild populations it may be when

167 commercial or recreational fishers, divers or the public notice dead or moribund aquatic
168 animals.

169 The steps of a formal outbreak investigation include a general description of the problem and
170 establishment of a case definition to enable counting of cases, leading to a description of the
171 temporal pattern (when?), the spatial pattern (where?) and the features of the affected animals
172 (who?). This assessment of the pattern of disease determines whether or not it is static or
173 propagating, arising from one or more sources, and includes the collection of environmental
174 data to rule out common problems such as hypoxia or pollution (toxicological) events.
175 Veterinary clinical examination and gross pathology, followed by relevant, selected
176 laboratory tests such as PCR, histopathology, microbiology, virology, parasitology and
177 serology are used to classify the type of disease and determine a known cause. All of this
178 requires coordination, optimally by an experienced aquatic animal health case manager or
179 veterinary diagnostician (Figure 1).

180 The availability of metagenomics in an established diagnostic system would mandate
181 collection and storage of representative samples at the end of stage I (Figure 1), that is, during
182 the outbreak, in anticipation that they may need to be tested. The benefit obtained through
183 this systematic process is an increase in the predictive value of the results of metagenomics;
184 this follows from increased prior probability that there is actually a disease present and that it
185 is infectious. Without this, there is a likelihood that the findings of metagenomics may be
186 “false positive” and have very low predictive value (Figure 2). Representatives of microbial
187 genera known to contain pathogenic taxa are frequently found in metatranscriptomic studies
188 of apparently healthy populations^{2,14} and by mere taxonomic association there could be
189 attributional misjudgement. The significance of prior probability (prevalence) in selection of
190 populations for laboratory tests cannot be overemphasized. For example, if only 1% of
191 populations actually have the infectious disease, the likelihood that a positive test result is
192 true in any of these populations is only 50% (no better than the toss of a coin), even if the test
193 has 99% sensitivity and 99% specificity. Conducting an epidemiological screen through a
194 formal outbreak investigation increases the prior probability; a modest increase to 20% has a
195 dramatic effect on the reliability of the omics analysis (Figure 2). The same comments apply
196 to the selection of samples from within a population – anything that can be done to select
197 samples most likely to be representative of the problem under investigation will be beneficial.
198 This means that a documented case definition and sample collection by an experienced
199 individual are more likely to yield useful results than *ad hoc* samples.

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Figure 2. Relationship between prior probability that an infectious disease is present in the population under investigation and the likelihood that the results of a metagenomic/metatranscriptomic screen are reliable, assuming 99% sensitivity and specificity of the omics approach. Figure based on data obtained from the literature³⁴.

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To demonstrate how metatranscriptomics can be applied during a disease outbreak, we use SARS-CoV-2 as an example. During December 2019, a patient showing clinical signs of respiratory disease was admitted to hospital in Wuhan, China³⁵. A few days after the disease had progressed, PCR and antigen detection kits were employed to test for suspected respiratory pathogens. Importantly, the results of each test were negative. To determine the causative agent, metatranscriptomic sequencing was performed on bronchoalveolar lavage fluid and results were available approximately 48 hours later³⁵. The similarity search using BLAST revealed a contig of 30,474 nucleotides that had 89% nucleotide sequence similarity to a bat coronavirus and grouped with sarbecoviruses (e.g. SARS-CoV) on phylogenetic trees. It was notable that, seemingly because of its strong association with respiratory disease, the novel coronavirus exhibited substantially high abundance (reads per million) and

216 remarkable coverage. Needless to say, the rapid detection of SARS-CoV-2 facilitated the
217 development of PCR and antigen tests as well as vaccines. In addition, rapid genome
218 sequencing provided a real-time analysis of virus evolution and the detection of novel
219 variants with varying levels of resistance and infectivity.

220 **Role of metagenomics in passive surveillance**

221 In addition to disease outbreaks, metagenomics serves as a cost-effective tool for passive
222 surveillance and ecosystem monitoring (Figure 3). Passive surveillance can be achieved by
223 using either samples of asymptomatic animals or the environment (i.e. eDNA/eRNA), which
224 both provide a variety of benefits³⁶. For example, unbiased passive surveillance using animal
225 samples can reveal potential tissue tropisms (often determined by comparing transcript
226 abundances of different organ types), identify natural pathogen reservoirs in the aquatic
227 environment, determine transmission links in aquatic wildlife, and identify beneficial
228 microorganisms within an aquaculture facility³⁷. Similarly, unbiased screening can help
229 investigate multifactorial diseases with unknown aetiologies; for example, revealing the total
230 assemblage of viruses, bacteria and eukaryotes that are associated with complex gill disease
231 in a single host³⁸.

232 Because metatranscriptomics also incorporates the expression of host genes, which generally
233 account for more than 90% of the composition of reads²⁹, these data could in theory be
234 utilised to examine the genetic basis of host resistance in parallel with pathogen discovery;
235 for example, measuring changes in gene expression of infected tissues or populations (e.g.
236 “infected” versus “uninfected”) or assessing the expression of biomarkers of reduced health.
237 It is also notable that water pollution – driven by anthropogenic processes – can facilitate
238 immunosuppression in aquatic animals³⁹. As such, linking pathogen discovery to pollutant
239 exposures and gene expression – through metatranscriptomics – will provide a more holistic
240 examination into the causes of aquatic animal diseases. In addition, the use of eDNA
241 eliminates invasive sampling and reduces the cost and time associated with handling aquatic
242 animal samples. Importantly, however, metatranscriptomic analyses of eDNA and animal
243 samples does have limitations, including fragmented DNA or RNA and potentially erroneous
244 host assignments³⁶.

245 **Figure 3. The importance of passive metatranscriptomic screening using the discovery of**
 246 ***Halichoeres melanurus* ranavirus as an illustrative example⁹.** (A) Phylogeny of the major capsid
 247 protein, which is a common gene targeted in PCR studies of iridoviruses⁹, reveals strong clustering of
 248 *H. melanurus* ranavirus – identified from a healthy ecosystem in the Great Barrier Reef, Australia –
 249 among SCRIV isolates associated with disease outbreaks in aquaculture (B) Alignment of the major
 250 capsid protein illustrates mutations among isolates. Shaded bases denote disagreements to the
 251 consensus sequence. The maximum likelihood phylogeny was estimated a nucleotide sequence
 252 alignment of the major capsid protein of all published SCRIV isolates available on NCBI/GenBank
 253 using MAAFT⁴⁰. The best-fit model of nucleotide substitution and phylogenetic tree were estimated
 254 using IQ-TREE (v.1.6.12) with 1000 bootstrap replicates⁴¹.

255 **Perspectives**

256 Rapid genomics-based analyses are central to mitigating infectious disease threats to global
257 aquaculture. Because of its unbiased nature and high resolution, we suggest incorporating
258 metagenomics and in particular metatranscriptomics as a central diagnostic tool for the rapid
259 detection of pathogens in aquaculture, particularly in the context of outbreak investigation.
260 Although metatranscriptomics is arguably the most sensitive and cost-effective method for
261 pathogen discovery, it is based on sequence analysis, and additional confirmation is required
262 (Figure 1). As such, the best practice for diagnosing aquatic animal diseases involves
263 combining metatranscriptomics with traditional diagnostic approaches (e.g., history
264 collection, necropsy and histopathology), environmental analysis and sound epidemiological
265 investigations of infectious disease patterns (Figure 1). For example, the metatranscriptomic
266 discovery of “salmon flavivirus” successfully incorporated gross pathology, histopathology,
267 cell culture and electron microscopy⁴². A pathogen is usually defined as a microorganism that
268 causes, or can cause, disease, and therefore investigating its effects on the host via *in vitro* or
269 *in vivo* studies is a critical step in the pathogen discovery process.

270 It is important to note, however, that the “gold standard” approach might not always be
271 feasible, especially for viruses that cannot be cultured, as well as discoveries made using
272 eDNA. The sole utilisation of metatranscriptomics will require the establishment of an
273 effective regulatory framework with clear guidelines for correctly defining and quantifying
274 the discovery of a suspected pathogen (i.e., how do we define a suspect case and what follow-
275 up investigations are required). We propose that the minimum analytical criteria for such
276 discoveries should encompass: (i) intact open reading frames (ii) phylogenetic validation of
277 the pathogen (iii) levels of transcript abundance indicative of infection or pathogen shedding
278 in the environment, (iv) the detection of core pathogen genes, and (v) the presence of the
279 suspected host or vector’s nucleic acid (for eDNA-based discoveries). For the future, it will
280 be important to establish a threshold level of pathogen reads that is consistent with disease in
281 the host (i.e. infection) and environment (i.e. shedding). For example, the viral load
282 considered to be consistent with mortality due to ostreid herpesvirus 1, the causative agent of
283 Pacific Oyster Mortality Syndrome (POMS), is 10^4 genome copies per mg oyster tissue⁴³.
284 Pathogen detection of notifiable diseases in animal industries, including livestock and
285 aquaculture, may have profound impacts on trade and commerce. Consequently, it is essential
286 to establish definitive guidelines that delineate suspicious cases and outline actions that
287 safeguard trade without compromising the protection of animal industries.

288 Despite recent advances in next-generation sequencing and its substantial reduction in cost,
289 the implementation of metatranscriptomics into aquaculture will require upskilling,
290 proficiency testing, user friendly bioinformatic tools, and open data sharing that enables rapid
291 analyses during an outbreak. International collaborative networks are crucial for tackling
292 outbreak investigations involving suspected novel pathogens requiring metatranscriptomics in
293 regions with limited expertise and technological capacity, thereby promoting resource equity
294 in areas where aquaculture is most prevalent. For example, “Nextstrain”
295 (www.nextstrain.org) has emerged as a valuable tool that provides a real-time phylogenetic
296 analysis of virus evolution during a disease outbreak that investigators can readily analyse⁴⁴.
297 In addition, artificial intelligence could be employed to generate a comprehensive diagnostic
298 report based on a variety of data sources including pathogen taxonomy (e.g. phylogenetics)
299 and immune gene expression (both derived from RNA sequencing), imaging (e.g.
300 histopathology, culture), environment (e.g. temperature, salinity, pH) and host biochemistry.

301 An important area for future consideration is incorporating an ecosystems approach into
302 surveillance programs. For instance, it is becoming increasingly evident that the aquatic
303 environment harbours a rich source of viral diversity that is naturally transmitted between
304 interacting organisms with no disease³⁷. Australia, one of the world’s 17 megadiverse
305 countries, leads in environmental biosecurity by implementing a national approach that
306 includes a list of priority exotic pests and diseases to protect its environment. However,
307 changes in the host-environment relationship triggered by environmental stressors (e.g.,
308 extreme weather events or environmental pollutants) may lead to disease emergence,
309 particularly in intense farming environments. It is therefore imperative that we direct our
310 sampling towards aquatic animals at the domestic-wild interface to identify sources of risk.
311 For example, metatranscriptomic sampling near open net cages where wild reservoirs may
312 interact with farmed species, or regular screening of wild sourced broodstock.

313 For decades, wild fisheries have remained stable, meanwhile aquaculture has grown by 6.6%
314 since 2020, accounting for approximately 60% of aquatic animal products for human
315 consumption¹. As aquaculture continues to expand, addressing the global infectious disease
316 crisis will require a rapid and unbiased diagnostic framework that is fit-for-purpose and
317 facilitates transparent data sharing and reporting. Crucially, the widespread integration of
318 genomics-based diagnostics in aquaculture will improve recognition and characterisation of
319 emerging diseases. However, it will also result in a multitude of novel microbial discoveries.

320 As such, an appropriate reporting framework with clear guidelines on how to quantify,
321 interpret and communicate risk associated with these data is imperative.

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